

Kinetics of the Enolisation of Cyclopentanone Catalysed by Amino Acids

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Kinetics of the enolisation of cyclopentanone has been studied in presence of glycine, β alanine and α -DL alanine. It is observed that the rate of enolisation is increased by the amino acid of larger dipole moment. The zwitterion form of the amino acids have been shown to catalyse the enolisation of the ketone at about pH 6.0. The effect of the change in concentration of amino acids, solvent isotope effect, solvent effect and the Arrhenius parameters etc. indicate the enolisation to be of bimolecular nature. The probable mechanism of the enolisation has been discussed in the light of observed data.

THE kinetics of the enolisation of ketones concerning their prototropic changes have been studied by Lapworth¹, Hughes, Watson and Yates². The usual methods, employed for the study of the conversion of keto into enol form, are the halogenation³, racemisation⁴ and deuteration⁵. The kinetic studies on the enolisation of aliphatic and aromatic ketones have been reported by a number of workers⁶⁻¹⁰ under different conditions. Shilov and Vasnikov¹¹ measured the rate of enolisation of acetone by the rate of its iodination in presence of glycine. The reaction was found to be of first order. In the presence of glycine the rate was proportional to the concentration of glycine. Recently Mhala and Singh¹² have reported the kinetics of the enolisation of cyclopentanone in presence of mineral acids and buffer medium and have discussed the probable mechanism. No kinetic data is available in the literature on the amino acid catalysed enolisation of cyclic ketones. In the present communication the kinetics of the enolisation of cyclopentanone catalysed by glycine, β alanine and α -DL alanine is reported.

Material and Methods

Glycine was of Laborchemie Apolda, Germany, α -DL alanine and β alanine used were of A.R. quality made in Poland. Cyclopentanone was of Fluka A.R. quality B.P. 129°.

Analytical grade inorganic and organic chemicals were used throughout the investigations. Deuterium oxide was supplied by Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay with a stated deuterium content of 99.4%.

The procedure adopted for the measurement of kinetics of enolisation was exactly the same as in previous communication.¹² The temperature of the

thermostat was maintained at $35^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The buffer solutions for kinetic experiments were made as mentioned by S.P.L. Sorenson^{13,14} and Clark^{15,16}.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of the enolisation of cyclopentanone (0.01M) was investigated at varying concentrations of glycine. The results (Table 1) show a first order dependence in glycine pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) in glycine calculated from the slopes of the linear log-time plots increase linearly with the increase in cyclopentanone concentration. The second order rate constants $k_e = k_1/\text{cyclopentanone}$ were calculated and the average value was obtained as 0.31 l. mole⁻¹. min.⁻¹, for the enolisation of cyclopentanone. The slope of the plot $\log k_1$ vs. $\log$ cyclopentanone (Fig. 1) was found to be approximately unity which stabilises a first order dependence in cyclopentanone concentrations.¹⁷

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs. $\log$ Cyclopentanone at glycine = 1M and temperature = 35°.

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TABLE 1—RATE COEFFICIENTS FOR THE ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE CATALYSED BY AMINO ACIDS

Amino acid (M)	2 + log (Acid M)	4 + log <i>k</i>		
		β Alanine	α DL Alanine	Glycine
0.40	1.60	2.02	1.38	0.89
0.80	1.90	2.61	2.02	1.40
1.20	2.07	2.86	2.30	1.84
1.60	2.20	3.06	2.51	2.11

Effect of change of iodine concentrations

Kinetic runs were made in varying concentrations of iodine keeping the constant concentrations of cyclopentanone and glycine. The constant values of rate constants (results not given) indicate zero order with respect to iodine.

Solvent effect

According to the qualitative theory of Ingold, the rate of the reaction should show elevation in rate by change over from water (more polar) to aqueous dioxan mixtures¹⁸ (less polar). Since dioxan media are well known for their proton donation from the acid medium, the rate increase in dioxan medium is expected to be more significant. It was therefore thought desirable to study the effect of the solvent on the rate of enolisation of cyclopentanone. Kinetic runs were carried out in 1.0M glycine. Table 2 summarises the results. Increase in the rate with the increase in dioxan supports the formation of the transition state in which charge is dispersed.

TABLE 2—RATE COEFFICIENTS FOR THE ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE IN DIOXAN-WATER MIXTURES V/V.

Cyclopentanone = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ Glycine = 1.0M Temperature = 35°		
Glycine (M)	% of Dioxane V/V	$k \times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)
1.0	0.0	2.52
1.0	5.0	3.12
1.0	10.0	5.16
1.0	15.0	8.24
1.0	20.0	10.01
1.0	25.0	12.80

Effect of temperature

Kinetic runs at different temperatures, to study the enolisation of cyclopentanone, were carried out at different concentrations of glycine. Figure 2 describes Arrhenius plots and Arrhenius parameters calculated from slopes of the linear plots are summa-

risied in Table 3. These parameters correspond to the bimolecular enolisation of cyclopentanone.

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plots for the glycine catalysed enolisation of cyclopentanone.

Cyclopentanone = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$

TABLE 3—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE CATALYSED BY GLYCINE

Cyclopentanone = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$			
Glycine (M)	<i>E</i> K.cal/mol	<i>A</i> (sec. ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (e.u.)
0.4	12.0	2.58×10^4	40.40
0.8	15.7	2.32×10^{11}	26.88
1.6	17.3	4.41×10^7	25.61

Solvent isotope effect

Use of D₂O in place of H₂O has been made to study its effect on the rates of reactions. Due to the mass difference between hydrogen and deuterium, reaction rates should be differently effected. The specific acid catalysed enolisation of cyclopentanone was supported by the observed faster rate in D₂O than thgt of H₂O.¹² A changeover from water to 70% deuterium oxide brings down the rate of enolisation of cyclopentanone ($k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} = 0.371$). This indicates that the stabilisation of the transition state formed out of glycine and neutral cyclopentanone will be more effective in water rather than in D₂O.

Kinetic runs were made using different concentrations of glycine, β alanine and α DL. alanine. These three amino acids were used to study the effects on the rates of enolisation because they are expected to have different effects by virtue of their different dipolemoments (glycine = 13.3, β alanine = 17.4 and α DL alanine 14.2). Table 1 summarises the results and Fig. 3 describes the plots between the log rates and log amino acids concentrations. It is clear from the plots that the rates of enolisation increase with the increase in the amino acids concentrations. Since the slopes of the linear curves increase with the increase in the dipolemoment of the amino acids, it may be concluded that the enolisation is stabilised by amino acids of larger dipolemoment. More is the

dipolemoment of the amino acid more is the separation of charge in the molecule. The ends of the

Fig. 3. Enolisation of cyclopentanone at 35° in glycine, β alanine and α DL alanine.

Cyclopentanone = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$.

amino acid molecule will, therefore, be more effective as acid and base during enolisation.

Zwitterion of glycine is almost cent percent at about pH 7 ($pK = 4.2$).¹⁹ Hence the fraction of the zwitterion species is 0.999 at pH 7. The fractions of the zwitterion species calculated at pH values 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7 are 0.66, 5.94, 38.70, 98.47 and 99.9% respectively. Since the rate of the enolisation of the cyclopentanone is proportional to the glycine concentration, hence it will be also proportional to the concentration of the zwitterion species.

On the basis of the experimental results, the probable mechanism of amino acid catalysed enolisation may be formulated (see next col.).

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References

1. A. LAPWORTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 30.
2. E. D. HUGHES, Watson and Yates, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3318.
3. P. D. BARLETT and C. H. STAUFFER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2580.
4. S. K. HSU, C. K. INGOLD and C. L. WILSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935.
5. K. H. B. NHOEFFER and O. REITZ, *Physik. Chem. A.*, 1937, 179.
6. P. D. BARLETT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 773.
7. T. G. BONNER, D. P. EVANS and H. B. WATSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1953.
8. L. ZÜCKER and L. P. HAMMETT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2779.
9. R. P. BELL and H. C. L. HIGGINS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 636.
10. C. G. SWAIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4578.
11. E. A. SHILOV and A. A. VASNIKOV, *Inst. Org. Chem. Acad. Sci., Ukrain, S.S.R., Kier, Doklady Nauk, S.S.S.R.*, 1952, 84, 297.
12. M. M. MHALA and K. J. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1975, 52, 1092.
13. S. P. L. SORENSON, *Biochem. Z.*, 1909, 21, 131.
14. S. P. L. SORENSON, *Ergeb. Physiol.*, 1912, 19, 393.
15. W. M. CLARK and H. A. LUBS, *Biol. Chem.*, 1916, 25, 479.
16. W. M. CLARK, "The determination of Hydrogen Ion", 3rd Edition, Chapter 9, The Williams Wilkins Co., Baltimore, Md., 1928.
17. S. P. MUSHRAN, K. C. GUPTA and R. SANEHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1974, 51, 146.
18. E. D. HUGHES and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 244.
19. F. FISHER. and M. FISHER, "Organic Chemistry", 1940, p. 412